

Sonocatalytic degradation of organic dye contaminants from water solutions using the novel NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite zeolite nanocomposite catalyst

Meysam Sadeghi¹

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University,
Khorramabad, Iran

meysamsadeghi1364@gmail.com

Pourya Zarshenas²

Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences
Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran

pouryazarshenas@yahoo.com

Abstract

In present study, NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite zeolite as a magnetically separable nanocomposite catalyst was successfully manufactured by the hydrothermal method. FESEM, EDX, FTIR, XRD, VSM and BET were used to analysis the as-synthesized nanocomposite. The sonocatalytic performance of NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite was then investigated on the degradation of organic dye contaminants, involving rhodamine B (RhB), methylene blue (MB) and methyl orange (MO) from water solutions. Several analytical parameters, like irradiation time, initial dye concentration, process type, catalyst dosage, H₂O₂ concentration, and organic dye type were considered to attain the maximum sonocatalytic activity. An ultrasound-assisted advanced oxidation process was applied to degrade MB, RhB and MO dyes over the NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite nanocomposite. The ultrasound-assisted NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite/H₂O₂ system removed 99.2% of MB (25 mg/L) within 14 min, which is 191 and 26.1 folds of that in the NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite/H₂O₂ and US/H₂O₂ systems, respectively. Trapping experiments demonstrated that free •OH radicals were the main reactive oxidative species for the degradation of MB dye via the sonocatalytic system. As well, the cycling experiments illustrated the suitable stability of NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite nanocomposite.

Keywords: NiFe₂O₄/MoS₂/clinoptilolite, zeolite, nanocomposite, catalyst, organic dyes, sonodegradation